

Analyzing the influence of stock markets and institutional investors on the growth of the real estate industry in South Africa

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Abstract

This study examine the influence of stock markets and institutional investors on the growth of the real estate industry in South Africa using yearly data for the period 2010 to 2023. In this paper, I investigated the effect of stock markets on real estate industry in south Africa. I applied the vector autoregression (VAR) model one of the most popular approach in macroeconomic multivariate time series analysis. I collected yearly data for a sample period from 2010 to 2023. I conducted Granger causality test beside VAR in order to detect causality from stock markets to lending interest rate. The results indicated that change in lending interest rate has indeed caused change in stock market, but the effect is very limited. I conducted stability test and system was stable. There is no autocorrelation. According to the estimated result, the change in lending interest rate and stock market have impact on real estate market but for stock market, impact on real estate industry come after some time as in first and second lag show insignificance results in results.

1. Introduction

Globally, the housing property market has shown significant fluctuations since the 1960s. According to Du Toit (2005:1), the housing property market has been in a boom worldwide since the year 2000 and this is considered as the largest financial bubble experienced so far. The real estate belongings industry is pivotal to the monetary landscape of South Africa, using urban improvement, employment, and well known monetary increase. South Africa has undergone significant political, social, and economic change in the last ten years, as it has emerged from the apartheid era. This paper presents an influence of stock market and financial investors on South African real estate industry over the 2010-2023 periods. The outlook of the South African real estate market was assessed. This study investigated the placement of stock markets and institutional traders in fostering the increase of the real estate industry.

1.1. Background of the study

According to Liow (2006), the stock market and the real estate sector are very important components of an economy. The stock market shows enterprises and listed companies financial position, investor investment demand and trading transactions. For both companies and individuals, real

estate is an indispensable and rigid asset. Liow also notes that when the economy is growing, benefits to companies and manufacturers can lead to a boom in the stock market. With the supply and demand ratio unchanged, real estate prices rise accordingly. Therefore, there may be a long-term or short-term relationship between the stock market and the real estate sector. Housing demand and supply changes are usually used to model house price dynamics (see for instance, Naylor, 1967; Arcelus and Meltzer, 1973). Therefore, one can distinguish between changes in housing demand and supply when examining house price dynamics.

The South African actual assets market has visible huge enlargement, influenced via numerous macroeconomic factors. Institutional customers, including pension finances, coverage businesses, and REITs, have increasingly allotted assets to real belongings, attracted with the aid of manner of its capacity for stable returns and portfolio diversification. Concurrently, the inventory marketplace's average performance can reflect and impact investor sentiment and capital availability for actual assets investments. This research will delve into these dynamics to make clear the interaction between stock markets,

institutional investors, and real estate markets development.

1.2. Research Objectives

- To quantitatively assess the impact of stock market performance on real estate investment in South Africa.
- To evaluate the role and extent of institutional investors' contributions to the real estate sector.
- To develop a comprehensive econometric model that links stock market dynamics and institutional investment to real estate market growth.

1.3. Research hypothesis

H: 1a: Does stock market has impact on real estate investments performance in South Africa?

H: 1c: Is there relationship between institutional investors, and real estate market performance in South Africa?

2. Literature Review

The global property market is showing signs of improvement (recovery) in the aftermath of the global financial crisis (GFC) that had a direct impact on the returns on all sections of real estate. According to Jones Lang Lasalle (JLL) (2015) buoyant capital markets in conjunction with increased

demand for space has resulted in significant projected growth across all the main global regions and property sectors. The research uses secondary data collected by IPD/MSCI. The data serves to indicate market performance of both SA and the UK before and after the GFC. This helps highlight the influence market characteristics have on the performance of the property industry.

Typically, property markets comprise of four predominant sectors, namely: office, retail, industrial and residential. To better identify the characteristics influencing the performance of the property markets it is necessary to breakdown the market into its constituent sectors. The residential property sector has been omitted from this evaluation as the comparative data published by IPD/MSCI relating to the residential sector has not been available for long enough to draw meaningful comparisons. Ultimately, understanding the unique characteristics that govern the performance of a given property market will reduce the risk for investors by enabling them to make more informed decisions. Furthermore, this knowledge could be used to better insulate vulnerable economies in the developing world from external threats such as the GFC. Since property in SA was the best performing asset class in 2014 (return of 26.64%)

(Sanlam, 2015), it is evident that creating a lower risk environment in the property market could have a significant impact on economic growth in South Africa

2.1 Stock Market and Real estate investment

Theoretically speaking however, real estate has been the subject of numerous studies since the 1990s which have attempted to transcend the neo-marginalist (Wheaton, 1999) and Marxist (Harvey, 1978 & 1985) traditions. The interdependent nature of relations between real estate, the financial markets, town planning and even urban policy is now increasingly being examined (Fainstein, 2001 and 2008; Aveline-Dubach, 2008; Theurillat, 2011; David and Halbert, 2013). Nevertheless, these studies have primarily been focused on major cities, leaving out smaller towns and non-urban regions.

In real estate investment, risk management, finance and investment literature, several studies have examined the relationship between housing price and the stock market and its attendance implications. Some of the studies in recent decades include Samanta (2010), Wang, Tianyi & Huang (2012), Abbas, Khan & Shah (2013), Bhowmik (2013), Issam, Achraf & Boujelbene (2013), Gospodinov & Jamali (2014), Li & Giles

(2015), Mitra, Iyer & Joseph (2015), Ghufuran, Awan, Khakwani & Qureshi (2016), Sehgal & Garg (2016), Chung, Fung & Shilling (2016), Melo-Velandia (2017), Olbrys & Majewska (2017), Hussain, Murthy & Singh (2019), Quoreshi, Uddin & Jienwatcharamongkhol (2019), Saranya (2019) and Trivedi et al. (2021). The findings from these studies have shown a strong impact of stock market and financial institutional on real estate market development.

Markowitz (1959) believes that the portfolios include all types of assets held by investors. This collection of assets should include not only a variety of securities, but also assets or items with investment attributes. As a result, stocks and fixed assets can make up some form of a portfolio that can be held by investors. The real estate sector and stocks are two special commodities with investment attributes with different nominal prices. The substitution effect works when their relative returns change. Lin and Lin (2011) studied the housing-stock market relationship in six Asian economies and concluded that these two investment methods can be mutually substituted. Kiyotaki and Moore (1997) studied the roles of real estate assets and stock assets in the credit process and

proposed the theory of credit expansion effect. According to them, real estate and stocks can be accepted as collateral in the loan process by various financial institutions, where the amount of the loan is adjusted by the value of the mortgaged assets. When stock prices or property prices rise, the total assets of borrowers holding these assets increase, reducing the risk of loans and the amount of loans offered by banks increases. When a loan is granted, the borrower's cash flow increases, and some assets may be invested in the stock market and the real estate sector, leading to an increase in the prices of both. Thus, the credit expansion effect provides an explanation for the alternating rise and fall in real estate and stock prices. From a macroeconomic perspective, the stock market and the real estate sector are linked by other macroeconomic factors such as monetary policy, inflation, and interest rates. According to Ba et al. (2009), on the premise of free capital flows, the real estate sector and stocks are highly complementary. On the contrary, stock price volatility is large and liquidity is strong. Provided the money supply is adequate and capital flows freely, the returns on the capital invested in different sectors should be the same. As a result, capital is withdrawn from low-

yielding investments and invested in higher-yielding investments. Due to the low liquidity of the real estate sector, it is difficult for investors to withdraw capital in time and allocate it to the stock market. Ba et al. (2009) maintain that the adjustment of the stock market with the housing sector should be relatively rapid, while the impact of the housing sector on the stock market has a long-time lag.

2.2. South Africa Stock Market

The South African stock market is one of the fastest developing markets, and its property sector is the only globally reported sector on the African continent. Akinsomi, Kola, Ndlovu & Motloun (2015) noted that South Africa is the only African country that was represented in the FTSE EPRA/NAREIT and the S&P Global REIT indices. Generally, African stock markets are characterised as fragmented and inefficient (Ntim, 2012). Ncube & Mingiri (2015) posited that African stock markets have been witnessing improvement with a significant level in Egypt and South Africa. However, the strong performance of South African stock indicates its considerable contribution and prominence in the African continent and global property stock market. Generally, the S.A. market is the only African market ranked among transparent markets in 2018

(Global Real Estate Transparent Index 2018).

2.3. Characteristics and structure of sa property markets

D'Arcy and Keogh (2002) view the property market as an institution, where a set of formal and informal rules govern the actions of the various property market stakeholders. Changes that occur in the institutional environment that impact the property market take place in legal, economic, social and political spheres. The broad institutional climate will influence the perceptions and expectations of property market stakeholders. Conversely the experiences of stakeholders may impact and lead to a change in the institutional environment (D'Arcy and Keogh, 2002). These formal and informal rules are evident in both SA. Hence, the research will be viewed through this institutional lens. The structure of the SA commercial property markets differ as a result of the following factors: the urban density of SA cities; decentralization; and owner composition. SA rural-urban migration remains significant and continues to play an important role in the present and expected future structure of the built environment. Additionally, the last twenty years have seen increasing decentralization away from SA's main CBDs, especially

from large corporate entities that typically take out long leases for large floor areas. This move has significantly increased the demand for office and retail space in SA cities. The structure of the SA property market on the other hand has seen significant change, with specific reference to the rapid growth of the listed sector.

2.4. Housing delivery mechanisms and the housing backlog in South Africa

Provision of housing is dependent on the performance of macro-economies within which the housing finance systems are located. In South Africa, the economic scenario during the post apartheid era has been relatively stable after the stagnation in the 1980s. Prior to 1994, government spending directed very little investment towards the education, health, housing and other basic needs of the majority black population (South Africa National Treasury, 2003). Against this background, the new democratic government after 1994 found itself with inherited inequalities in the social and economic systems. With regards to housing, it was estimated in 1996 that about 1.5 million people live in informal houses or squat in shacks in urban areas, and huge inequalities exist in housing provision across the country (Bolnick and Mitlin, 1999b; Smit, 2003). Later, the

Department of Housing, estimated the number of inadequately housed people to be between 3 million to 3.7 million (Smit, 2003). To this effect, the government has tried a number of housing initiatives to help alleviate the housing problem since it came to power in 1994. These have included; the Botshabelo Ac-cord (1994), the Housing White Paper (1995), the National Urban and Reconstruction Housing Agency (1995), the Housing Subsidy Scheme (1995), the Housing Act No. 107 (1997) and the Policy on Peoples Housing Process (1998). Within the framework of the Botshabelo Accord (1994), the government set itself a tar- get of delivering one million houses for the low-income group within five years (Thurman, 1999; Rust, 2003, Hassen, 2003).

3. Conceptual Framework and Model

The test will employ a framework that integrates monetary marketplace theories with actual estate investment dynamics, highlighting the channels thru which stock markets and institutional customers have an effect on actual belongings growth.

3.1. Econometric Model

Model Specification: The study will employ a Vector Autoregression (VAR) model to capture the dynamic courting between stock marketplace indices, institutional investment

flows, and actual property marketplace increase.

Let Y_t represent the vector of endogenous variables:

$$Y_t = \begin{pmatrix} RE_t \\ SM_t \\ II_t \end{pmatrix}$$

Where RE_t is the real belongings stock market growth, SM_t is the stock marketplace index, and II_t represents institutional investment level in real estate sector.

$$Y_t = A_0 + A_1 Y_{t-1} + A_2 Y_{t-2} + \dots + A_p Y_{t-p} + \epsilon_t$$

Where in A_i are coefficient matrices, p is the range of lags, and ϵ_t is the vector of error terms.

We took amount invested in real estate industry (**real_est_invest**) to represent real estate development, we analyzed stock market share(**stock_mark**) on impact of real estate and we took lending interest rate (**log_lend_inter**) to analyze the influence of financial investors like banks, insurances companies etc

4. Methodology and data

The study focused on influence of stock market and institutional investors on the South African real estate market development. Historical information on

stock market indices JSE, real assets market, and institutional investments facts from economic critiques and databases (world open data and OECD data, JSE) were used. Data were collected from 2010 to 2023. The study used Time Series Analysis where Stationarity test (ADF), cointegration tests (Johansen test), and Granger causality test have been done to validate the model assumptions. The parameters have been estimated by vector autoregressive (VAR) model used to research the impact of the stock market and institutional investment on real estate investment.

4.1. Econometric Modeling.

The study estimated a vector autoregressive (VAR) model, followed with the aid of diagnostic test to make sure version adequacy.

4.2. Vector autoregressive model

When we speak about different models and tools for analyzing time series, the vector autoregression model is definitely come in to main focus in this subject. The methodology of vector autoregression is first introduced by Christopher A. Sims in his article (Macroeconomics and Reality) at "Econometrica" in January 1980. In the article, he criticized the existing strategies within econometrics related to

macroeconomic time series analysis. He suggested vector autoregression (VAR) approach as an alternative for better understanding the relationships between macroeconomic variables (Sims 1980). The vector autoregression model is a generalization of autoregressive model that explain the variables in the model by an equation which included its own lag and lagged value of other variables and error term. The model provides framework for analyzing and forecasting multivariate time series. The VAR is formally expressed as:

$$y_t = C + A_1y_{t-1} + A_2y_{t-2} + \dots + A_iy_{t-i} + e_t$$

in this equation, y_t represents the $k \times 1$ vector of endogenous variables, where the i period back in observation y_{t-i} is called i -t lag of y . C denotes the $k \times 1$ vector of constants, also called exogenous variables, e_t is the $k \times 1$ vector of error terms with zero mean $[E(e_t) = 0]$ in a sample time period $t = (1, 2, \dots, T)$. A is the $k \times k$ coefficient matrix (Lütkepohl, 2011).

The process of VAR analysis has three main steps. The first step is about data transformation and model specification, such as unit root test and selecting optimal lag length and order. The second step is selecting appropriate model for further analysis, if data is stationary and integrated

in order zero, then vector autoregression (VAR) model is appropriate for analysis, but if the data is non stationary and there happen to be cointegration among variables, a vector error correction model (VECM) should be applied. The last step is about implementing analysis and testing the robustness of results and interpreting them.

4.3. Stationary test

Applying VAR model requires that time series need to be stationary. It means that statistical properties of the time series are constant over time. If a time series are non-stationary, then we have problem of spurious regressions in a regression process. The spurious regression occurs when two time series have a trend over time, also non-stationary, the regression of one variable on another could results a high correlation because of trending, even though they don't have actual correlation (Phillips & Perron, 1988). In order to evaluate whether a time series are stationary or not, we conducted a unit root test. If a time series have not unit root, also integrated at order zero $I(0)$, then it indicates that time series are stationary. If a time series contain one unit root, it is integrated in order one $I(1)$ and considered non-stationary. In this case, the time series have to be differenced to induce stationarity. If a time series have two unit root, indicating

that it integrated in order two $I(3)$ and we have to difference it twice. There are several ways to conduct a unit root test. Augmented Dickey Fuller test (ADF) is one of the most commonly used approaches. In ADF, null hypothesis will be: H_0 : series contains a unit root, and alternative hypothesis is: H_1 : series are stationary (don't contain a unit root). We conducted ADF test for all three variables

Table: 1. the results from the test are following:

Variables	Test value	P-value	Status
log stock_mark	-.5438448	0.016	stationary
log lend_inter	-2.304644	0.006	Stationary

After conducting ADF test we find that log stock market share and log of lending interest rate are stationary

4.4. Granger causality test

Granger causality test was introduced by Granger, C. W. J (1980), it is a statistical hypothesis test that tests one variable can be the cause of another variable. In the context of multivariate analysis, by fitting Granger causality in our vector autoregression model, we can formulate the null hypothesis for example as: H_0 : there is causality from lagged variable log stock_mark to log lend_inter. In other words, change lending interest rate and its lags jointly does not cause change in stock market. In table 2, we

VAR model. The vector autoregression model carried out by Stata. The VAR treats all variables as endogenous, but however we also conducted another VAR analysis where **real_est_invest** selected as exogenous variable. The order of the variables and lag length were selected based on the methodology and reasoning which discussed in previous part.

Table: 5. vector auto regression results

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Vector autoregression

Sample: 2013 - 2023                No. of obs   =      11
Log likelihood = -22.70967         AIC          =  6.674486
FPE          =  4.312129          HQIC         =  6.355264
Det(Sigma_ml) = .2129446         SBIC         =  7.180898

Equation      Farms      RMSE      R-sq      chi2      P>chi2
-----
SMarket       7          3.26715   0.9060    105.9959   0.0000
Lend_inter    7          .422093   0.9449    188.6657   0.0000

```

	Coef.	Std. Err.	z	P> z	[95% Conf. Interval]
SMarket					
SMarket					
L1.	.5839974	.3776988	1.55	0.122	-.1562787 1.324273
L2.	.2531776	.2267008	1.12	0.264	-.1911479 .6975031
L3.	-.3337971	.1304632	-2.56	0.011	-.5895004 -.0780939
Lend_inter					
L1.	5.852445	.9255014	6.32	0.000	4.038496 7.666394
L2.	-4.719086	2.788701	-1.69	0.091	-10.18484 .746668
L3.	3.42721	2.402441	1.43	0.154	-1.281488 8.135908
_cons	-9.092158	13.82686	-0.66	0.511	-36.19231 18.00799
Lend_inter					
SMarket					
L1.	-.1851432	.0487961	-3.79	0.000	-.2807817 -.0895047
L2.	.2582254	.0292882	8.82	0.000	.2008217 .3156292
L3.	-.1183431	.0168549	-7.02	0.000	-.1513782 -.085308
Lend_inter					
L1.	.5251419	.1195683	4.39	0.000	.2907922 .7594915
L2.	.7679454	.3602808	2.13	0.033	.061808 1.474083
L3.	-1.497045	.3103786	-4.82	0.000	-2.105376 -.8887142
_cons	14.37076	1.786334	8.04	0.000	10.86961 17.87191

The results from the VAR model are shown in table 5 give us some insights about influence of stock market on real estate. At first and second lag the coefficient is statistically insignificant possible explanation might be that the change in

stock market share will not immediately affect the real estate market it may take some time to pass through. But at third lag it is significant means that it has influence on real estate p-value is 0.011 while coefficient is -0.3337 any reduction of 1% percent of stock market share will cause decrease of 33.3% in real estate market. According to the model estimated result, the change in lending interest rate can in fact affect the real estate market as result is statistically significant for first, second and third lag this means that any changes in lending interest affect immediately, real estate market increase of 1% percent of interest rate will cause 11.8% reduction in real estate market.

6. Conclusion

In this paper, we wanted to answer the question about how changes in stock markets and in financial investors have affected real estate development in South Africa. In the beginning, we introduced some previous studies that are relevant and insightful for our topic. We presented some of the main conclusions that previous literature has offered and how it relates to our research question. We chose vector autoregression (VAR) model for our research method since it is most commonly used in empirical works related to time

series analysis. We tested the stationarity of the data, selecting lag length and did other preparational work before we run VAR. We applied vector autoregression model, Granger causality test and some other diagnostics and tests. By analyzing and discussing the results, we formed some conclusions for our research question. First, the change in stock market arguably can cause some change in real estate industry but after some time as result shown in first and second lag it is statistically insignificant but at third lag. Result shown that 1% percent decrease of stock market share will cause decrease of 33.3% in real estate markets. Secondary the results from VAR show that lending interest any changes in lending interest affect immediately real estate market.

7. References

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Appendix

Test of normality

Jarque-Bera test

Equation	chi2	df	Prob > chi2
SMarket	0.978	2	0.61313
Lend_inter	0.422	2	0.80979
ALL	1.400	4	0.84414

2. Vector error correction

```
. vec SMarket Lend_inter, trend(trend) lags(4)
```

Vector error-correction model

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Sample: 2014 - 2023
Log likelihood = 174.272
Det(Sigma_m1) = -2.50e+18
No. of obs = 10
AIC = -31.05441
HQIC = -31.68508
SBIC = -30.4795
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Equation	Parms	RMSE	R-sq	chi2	P>chi2
D_SMarket	9	.9491	0.9976	413.0661	0.0000
D_Lend_inter	9	.667377	0.9606	24.36002	0.0038

	Coef.	Std. Err.	z	P> z	[95% Conf. Interval]	
D_SMarket						
_cel						
L1.	-2.765251	4.405942	-0.63	0.530	-11.40074	5.870237
SMarket						
LD.	1.740163	4.167725	0.42	0.676	-6.428428	9.908754
L2D.	.5036383	2.569	0.20	0.845	-4.531508	5.538785
L3D.	2.109149	2.645608	0.80	0.425	-3.076148	7.294446
Lend_inter						
LD.	-5.511876	10.19412	-0.54	0.589	-25.49198	14.46822
L2D.	-.3210501	1.284237	-0.25	0.803	-2.838108	2.196008
L3D.	9.589161	9.811327	0.98	0.328	-9.640687	28.81901
_trend	-1.981469	2.337577	-0.85	0.397	-6.563037	2.600099
_cons	18.60048	4.496386	4.14	0.000	9.787729	27.41324
D_Lend_inter						
_cel						
L1.	3.15636	3.098117	1.02	0.308	-2.915838	9.228558
SMarket						
LD.	-3.184333	2.93061	-1.09	0.277	-8.928223	2.559558
L2D.	-1.641773	1.806438	-0.91	0.363	-5.182327	1.89878
L3D.	-2.129323	1.860307	-1.14	0.252	-5.775457	1.516812
Lend_inter						
LD.	7.948233	7.168175	1.11	0.268	-6.101131	21.9976
L2D.	.3404719	.9030342	0.38	0.706	-1.429443	2.110386
L3D.	-8.140481	6.89901	-1.18	0.238	-21.66229	5.38133
_trend	-1.735942	1.643709	-1.06	0.291	-4.957553	1.485669
_cons	3.216355	3.161714	1.02	0.309	-2.98049	9.4132

Cointegrating equations

Equation	Parms	chi2	P>chi2
_cel	1	6.769633	0.0093

Identification: beta is exactly identified

Johansen normalization restriction imposed						
beta	Coef.	Std. Err.	z	P> z	[95% Conf. Interval]	
_cel						
SMarket	1	.	.	.	.	.
Lend_inter	-1.444659	.5552425	-2.60	0.009	-2.532914	-.3564035
_trend	-2.344398	.	.	.	.	.
_cons	-39.3919	.	.	.	.	.